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2 Javier Pérez-González
3 Biology & Ethology Unit, University of Extremadura
4 Veterinary Faculty, University of Extremadura, 10071 Cáceres, Spain
5 Tel.: 34 927 257150, Fax: 34 927 257110
6 jpergon@unex.es

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9 **Relative effect of food Supplementation and Natural Resources on**
10 **Female Red Deer Distribution in a Mediterranean ecosystem**

11 JAVIER PÉREZ-GONZÁLEZ, Biology & Ethology, University of Extremadura, 10071
12 Cáceres, Spain

13 A. MÁRCIA BARBOSA, Rui Nabeiro Biodiversity Chair, CIBIO / University of Évora,
14 Largo dos Colegiais, 7004-516 Évora, Portugal;

15 Department of Biological Sciences, Imperial College London, Silwood Park Campus,
16 Ascot (Berkshire) SL5 7PY, United Kingdom

17 JUAN CARRANZA, Biology & Ethology, University of Extremadura, 10071 Cáceres, Spain;
18 Ungulate Research Unit, CRCP, University of Córdoba, 14071 Córdoba, Spain.

19 JERÓNIMO TORRES-PORRAS, Ungulate Research Unit, CRCP, University of Córdoba,
20 14071 Córdoba, Spain.

21 **ABSTRACT** Supplementary feeding is a widespread game management practice in several
22 red deer (*Cervus elaphus*) populations, with important potential consequences on the biology
23 of this species. In Mediterranean ecosystems food supplementation occurs in the rutting
24 period, when it may change mating system characteristics. Here we study the role of food
25 supplementation relative to natural resources in the spatial distribution, aggregation, and mean
26 harem size of hinds in Iberian red deer (*Cervus elaphus hispanicus*) during the rut. We studied
27 30 red deer populations of south-western Spain, 63 % of which experienced supplementary
28 feeding. Using multivariate spatial analyses we found that food supplementation affected the

29 distribution of females at 95 % of the populations at which it occurs. When green meadows
30 were present during the mating season, they acted as an important natural resource
31 influencing hind distribution. Additionally, the level of hind aggregation and mean harem size
32 were significantly higher in those populations where food supplementation determined hind
33 distribution than in populations where hind distribution did not depend on supplementary
34 feeding. Since hind aggregation and mean harem size are key elements in sexual selection,
35 supplementary feeding may constitute an important anthropogenic element with potential
36 evolutionary implications for populations of Iberian red deer.

37 **KEYWORDS** *Cervus elaphus*, environmental resources, female aggregation, mating system,
38 Mediterranean ecosystems, spatial analyses.

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40 Supplementary feeding of ungulate game species during seasons of low food abundance is a
41 common management practice in many countries of Europe, as well as in North America
42 (Guillett et al. 1996, Gundersen et al. 2004, Putman and Staines 2004). Low winter
43 temperatures and the presence of snow compel managers to supply food to deer in order to
44 maintain their body condition and fecundity, to increase overwinter survival, to reduce the
45 damage caused to agriculture and forestry, and to produce trophy antlers (Klein 1985, Putman
46 and Staines 2004). In red deer (*Cervus elaphus*) populations, food supplementation is
47 particularly common and may have important consequences (Smith 2001, Putman and Staines
48 2004). These consequences can be beneficial: body condition enhancement (Putman and
49 Langbein 1992, Kozak et al. 1995) or increase of male antler size (Rossler 1983). These
50 effects may also not occur (Groot Bruinderink et al. 2000), or even be harmful for deer
51 populations (Smith 2001, Schmidt and Hoi 2002, Miller et al. 2003), vegetation (Smith 2001,
52 Cooper et al. 2006) and other community levels (Côté et al. 2004). Food supplementation is

53 likely not neutral regarding several physiological, ecological and evolutionary features of red
54 deer populations.

55 In the regions of Europe with a Mediterranean climate, such as south-western Spain,
56 winters are mild and the limiting seasons are summer and early autumn (Bugalho and Milne
57 2003, Olea et al. 2005), when drought can severely reduce food availability. It is at this time,
58 which includes the rutting period of red deer, when some managers supply supplementary
59 food (such as maize, alfalfa pellets, or silage) in certain areas of their land. Some managers
60 also seed crops (usually cereals such as oat, barley or wheat) during spring for animals to
61 graze during summer, and these crops often remain present until autumn. Since the
62 distribution of food resources normally determines hind (female) movements, food
63 supplementation during the rut may affect the mating system (Emlen and Oring 1977,
64 Carranza 1992, Shuster and Wade 2003). Supplementary food supply increases hind
65 aggregation (Carranza et al. 1995, Sánchez-Prieto et al. 2004) and, consequently, male mating
66 strategies are likely to change from harem defence (Clutton-Brock et al. 1982) to resource
67 defence (Carranza et al. 1990, 1995, 1996). In addition, hind aggregation tends to increase
68 harem size and the degree of polygyny (Sánchez-Prieto et al. 2004), so that food
69 supplementation in Mediterranean areas can also affect sexual selection and, consequently, it
70 can have important evolutionary consequences for red deer populations (Andersson 1994).

71 Several studies have addressed the effect of food supplementation in red deer (reviewed
72 in Putman and Staines 2004; see Sánchez-Prieto et al. 2004 for Iberian red deer). In this work
73 we focus on the relative importance of food supplementation and natural resources over the
74 distribution of red deer hinds and their monopolization by males in Mediterranean
75 ecosystems. For that we first estimate the frequency of food supplementation practices in red
76 deer populations of south-western Spain. Secondly we build predictive models in order to
77 determine the effects of several natural and supplementary resources on hind distribution in

78 each studied population. Third, we determine the relative importance of supplementary food
79 in relation to natural resources over hind aggregation and mean harem size. Finally we discuss
80 possible implications of these practices on the biology and evolution of red deer populations,
81 focusing on mating system and sexual selection-related processes.

82 **STUDY AREA**

83 In Spain, Iberian red deer (*Cervus elaphus hispanicus*) populations inhabit mostly
84 private hunting estates located in Mediterranean ecosystems. These ecosystems have two
85 types of general vegetation formations: Mediterranean scrubland and open pasture areas
86 called *dehesa* (Olea et al. 2005). The scrubland is composed of species such as *Quercus ilex*,
87 *Quercus suber*, *Arbutus unedo*, *Phillyrea angustifolia*, *Olea europaea*, and several *Cistus*
88 species, among others. Areas covered by Mediterranean scrub and forest constitute refuge
89 zones and, mainly during summer (Rodríguez-Berrocal 1979), feeding areas. The *dehesas* are
90 mainly covered by pasture and dispersed *Quercus* trees. Deer use *dehesas* as both feeding
91 areas and rutting arenas. The *dehesa* productivity fluctuates seasonally and it can be divided
92 into two seasons: high and low productivity. Maximum productivity occurs during late
93 autumn, winter and spring, with the presence of *Quercus* acorns and green grass. During
94 summer and early autumn (dry season), the *dehesa* productivity falls abruptly (Olea et al.
95 2005). In this period *dehesas* consist mostly of a dry lawn with patches of different quantity
96 or quality. There are rich but scattered natural resources. For example, there can be green
97 meadows where the moisture level allows it. There can be perennial plants or shrubs such as
98 *Juncus holoschoenus* or *Rubus ulmifolius*, located on dry or damp stream beds. Lastly, there
99 are ponds that become the water supply for the animals in the rutting season. These natural
100 features, together with supplementary feeding, constitute the environmental factors that can
101 influence female red deer distribution during the rut.

102 In Mediterranean ecosystems of the Iberian Peninsula red deer density ranges from 0.1
103 to 1.0 individuals per hectare, averaging around 0.3 individuals per hectare (Carranza J.
104 Alarcos S, Torres-Porras J, Sánchez-Prieto C, Pérez-González J, Castillo L, Valencia J,
105 unpublished data). These high densities can be sustained because of the ecological
106 characteristics of the Mediterranean ecosystems (Carranza et al., in preparation).

107 **METHODS**

108 **Populations and variables**

109 We studied the red deer populations of 30 hunting estates in south-western Spain: 14 in
110 the Extremadura region and 16 in the Andalucía region (Figure 1). The estates had an average
111 area of 1,211.15 ha (± 756.39). The *dehesas* of these estates, where we focussed our field
112 work, had an average area of 320.21 ha (± 292.21).

113 In south-western Spain the rutting season of red deer normally occurs in September.
114 The duration of the rut varies among populations and years depending of weather factors and
115 food availability, but it is around 20 days. The peak of the rut (around 5 days of higher
116 activity) also occurs at different dates among populations and years. Within any day, rutting
117 activity is higher at dawn and dusk and lower at midday. Across the red deer range, males
118 present a harem defence mating strategy. However in the Iberian Peninsula, because of the
119 scarcity of resources during the breeding season and when the number of females per ha is
120 higher than 3.5 (Carranza et al. 1996), males can adopt a resource defence strategy in which
121 they defend territories rather than mobile harems (Carranza et al. 1990, 1995, 1996).

122 During the rut, adult males pursue mating rather than feeding (Clutton-Brock et al.
123 1982), so they are not directly driven by the environmental resources. Hinds form matrilineal
124 groups in which calves and sub-adult females follow the movements of the adult hinds
125 (Clutton-Brock et al. 1982), so we based our hind distribution analyses on the location of
126 adult females (more than one year old).

127 Within an estate, the area of *dehesa* can be divided in several pasture patches that are
128 traditionally used under a multi-year rotational scheme for cropping and grazing by livestock.
129 For each pasture patch we measured the percentage of plant cover (*Past cover*) as an index of
130 quantity, and the proportion of leguminous plants (*Past legum*) as a measure of quality, as
131 their high nitrogen content is important in plant-herbivore interactions (Whitehead 2000).
132 Other natural factors included the distance to green meadows (*Green mead*), to ponds
133 (*Ponds*), and to stream beds (*Stream*). Factors related to game management practices were the
134 distance to crop lands (*Crops*) and to food supplementation sites (*Food supp*).

135 **Data collection**

136 For each estate, with the help of aerial orthophotographs, we mapped the *dehesa* areas,
137 registering the distribution of environmental features such as ponds, streams and crops. We
138 then confirmed the location of these features by *in situ* observations. We estimated the
139 percentage of pasture cover and proportion of leguminous plants using 25x25 cm sampling
140 frames divided into four quadrants (following Carranza et al. 1990). Pasture characterization
141 took place during spring of 2004 in the estates of Extremadura, and in spring of 2005 in those
142 of Andalucía. The areas with the best pasture patches during spring can attract many
143 individuals that fertilize them, so that these areas usually remain as good-quality patches all
144 over the year (Whitehead 2000). During the rutting season (September 2004 in Extremadura;
145 September 2005 in Andalucía) we recorded the location of food supplementation sites and
146 green meadows. All maps were digitized and included in a Geographic Information System
147 (GIS) using ArcView 3.2 (ESRI, USA).

148 The spatial location of red deer individuals were recorded in September 2004 (in
149 Extremadura) and September 2005 (in Andalucía). In each estate we made car journeys in the
150 vehicle of the land manager at 10-20 Km/hour. Managers continually travel within the estates,
151 so the animals ignored us, which minimized recording the same individual more than once.

152 Surveys were always performed by at least two observers (the manager and a researcher), at
153 sunset (between 17:00 and 19:00 solar time) and during the peak of the rut (following
154 managers' advice). We recorded the presence of all individuals, indicating their sex and
155 estimated age class (yearling and adults (≥ 2 years old)). With these counts we determined the
156 number of females and the sex ratio for each population (yearling males were excluded from
157 all calculations and analyses (Clutton-Brock et al. 1997)). Also, with the help of maps, a
158 video camera and a Global Positioning System (GPS), we georeferenced all individuals
159 observed and included their spatial coordinates in the GIS. These surveys were done covering
160 the full area the animals use as arenas during the breeding season (following estate manager's
161 information). With this survey methodology we recorded the location of all individuals with
162 potential breeding interactions in a moment of relevant breeding activity for each population.

163 To assess the possible bias caused by this one-time ("snapshot") data collection
164 procedure (which was the only one possible for most of the estates), in one population we
165 carried out five different counts on different days during the rutting period (13, 14, 15, 16 and
166 22 of September 2005). In this way we assessed the repeatability of our punctual data
167 collection and compared the results obtained with each of the different surveys.

168 **Spatial processing**

169 Spatial models were based on a quadrangular grid defining the territorial units. Grid cell
170 size (scale grain) was established according to the mean spatial scale of the hind distribution
171 patterns for the studied populations, measured using Ripley's K statistic, a second-order
172 analysis based on the variance in the distance between points (Ripley 1981, Dale 1999, Diggle
173 2003). This method describes the characteristics of the point distribution pattern over a range
174 of distance scales, estimating the expected number of points within a distance t of an arbitrary
175 point in the study area. The scale of female distribution was determined by quantifying the
176 Ripley's K function in a range of distances (t). To determine if the spatial pattern reached a

177 significant aggregation we used 1,000 Monte Carlo simulations. Ripley's K analysis was also
178 used to estimate hind aggregation (Diggle 2003). Ripley's K analyses and Monte Carlo
179 simulations were implemented with ADE-4 (Thioulouse et al. 2001).

180 Grids of the established cell size were generated with ArcView 3.2. Using Idrisi
181 Kilimanjaro (Clark Labs, USA) we converted all maps to raster format and calculated, for
182 each grid cell, the total number of hinds and the mean value of each of the environmental
183 variables.

184 We used the spatial distribution of males and females to obtain estimates of the
185 distribution of males' breeding success. Here we used mean harem size (H) as an estimation
186 of skewness of male breeding success (Shuster and Wade 2003). Harem size was estimated as
187 the number of females within the area of influence of any mature male. To determine the area
188 of influence of each male, we used male spatial positions to create a Dirichlet tessellation
189 based on Thiessen polygons (Okabe et al. 1992, Dale 1999). The Thiessen polygon for an
190 individual can be interpreted as the dominion of this individual (Mithen et al. 1984). During
191 the peak of the rut females are normally distributed in groups held by a mature male. The
192 holding males expel other males from the area occupied by their female groups (Clutton-
193 Brock et al. 1982). In this case, the harem held by a male is included within the area of
194 influence (the Thiessen polygon) of this male. However, there could be some females that do
195 not belong to any harem. These females without holding males were included in the dominion
196 of the nearest male because in the oestrous time they look for the protection of holding males
197 against sexual harassment (Carranza and Valencia 1999).

198 **Statistical analyses**

199 We used Generalized Linear Models (GLM) with Poisson distribution and logarithmic
200 link function to build predictive models with the number of hinds per grid cell as the
201 dependent variable and the environmental variables as independent factors. GLM with

202 Poisson distribution is recommended for count data (Vincent and Haworth 1983, Guisan and
203 Zimmermann 2000). Models were implemented with R 3.2.1 software (R Development Core
204 Team 2008). Prior to modelling, we checked for collinearity between environmental variables
205 using Spearman's rank correlation coefficient. If the correlation between two variables was
206 higher than 0.7, one of the variables was eliminated based on biological significance and
207 expert opinion. Thus, for instance, under high correlation between pasture cover and the
208 proportion of leguminous plants, we used the latter because it has an important ecological
209 effect on ungulate feeding (Whitehead 2000).

210 To take spatial autocorrelation into account, we included in the GLM the spatial
211 coordinates according to the polynomial form proposed by Borcard et al. (1992): x coordinate,
212 y coordinate, x^2y , xy^2 , x^3 , and y^3 . If one of these variables entered a regression model, it meant
213 there was a significant spatial trend not accounted for by the environmental factors analysed,
214 and that could be attributed to spatial autocorrelation (Legendre 1993, Vargas et al. 2007).

215 We initially ran the GLM with all non-collinear environmental variables (both natural
216 and supplementary) and the spatial coordinates. By using the *step* function in R, we simplified
217 each model based on Akaike's Information Criterion (AIC). In the resultant models for each
218 population we considered an environmental factor a resource if it presented the expected
219 relationship with hind abundance: pasture cover and percentage of leguminous plants were
220 expected to be positively related with hind abundance; the distances to green meadows,
221 ponds, stream beds, crop lands and food supplementation sites were expected to have a
222 negative coefficient.

223 Finally, we compared hind density, hind aggregation and mean harem size between the
224 populations in which hind distribution was and was not related to food supplementation sites.

225 **RESULTS**

226 The mean value of hind spatial pattern scale (t^*) was 49.5 m (± 5.82 m). Therefore, we
227 used a grid cell size of 50x50-m as spatial modelling units. In all the estates hinds showed a
228 significantly aggregated distribution (1,000 Monte Carlo simulations, $P < 0.05$ for all the
229 estates). Using the distribution data obtained from surveys done on different days did not
230 significantly change the results for the population tested (see online supplementary material).

231 Table 1 summarizes the results for the GLM model obtained for each estate (see online
232 supplementary material for the entire results of the GLM). For 29 of the 30 estates (96.7 %) at
233 least one analyzed environmental variable was associated significantly with the number of
234 hinds per grid cell. In the only estate for which no environmental variables were related to
235 hind distribution (CC in online supplementary material) the number of counted hinds (26) was
236 low relative to the other populations in this study.

237 Food supplementation occurred in 19 (63.3 %) of the 30 estates studied (Fig. 2). In 18
238 (94.7 %) of the estates where it occurred, food supplementation significantly affected hind
239 distribution, and in 16 of these estates it was the most important factor (Table 1, Fig. 2). Crop
240 lands occurred in 6 estates (20 %) and were associated with hind distribution in 3 of them
241 (Table 1, Fig. 2). The presence of green meadows only occurred on 2 estates, but when it was
242 present it was the most important resource (Table 1, Fig. 2). The remaining environmental
243 factors (Past cover, Past legum, Ponds and Streams) occurred more frequently but they acted
244 as significant resources in less than 50 % of the cases (Table 1, Fig. 2). See also online
245 supplementary material for the predicted values given by each model.

246 The area covered during the car journeys did not differ between the estates in which
247 hind distribution was not related to food supplementation (Without Food Supp estates) (mean
248 \pm SE = 290.15 \pm 97.13 ha) and those in which it was (With Food Supp estates) (mean \pm SE =
249 301.84 \pm 75.50 ha, Table 2). Hind density (number of hinds divided by the area covered in the
250 car journeys) was not significantly different between Without Food Supp estates (mean \pm SE

251 = 0.22 ± 0.26 hinds per ha) and With Food Supp estates (mean \pm SE = 0.85 ± 0.20 hinds per
252 ha), although there was a trend towards higher density in With Food Supp estates (Table 2).
253 Hind aggregation was significantly higher in With Food Supp estates (mean \pm SE = $28.54 \pm$
254 5.24 females within t^* , Table 2, Fig. 3) than in Without Food Supp estates (mean \pm SE = 3.42
255 ± 6.74 females within t^*). Mean harem size was significantly higher in With Food Supp
256 (mean \pm SE = 4.25 ± 0.27 hinds per harem, Table 2, Fig. 3) estates than in Without Food Supp
257 estates (mean \pm SE = 2.70 ± 0.35 hinds per harem). As an additional result, the sex ratio
258 (number of males divided by the number of females) was not different between Without Food
259 Supp estates (mean \pm SE = 0.67 ± 0.10) and With Food Supp estates (mean \pm SE = $0.50 \pm$
260 0.08 , Table 2).

261 Figure 4 shows the relationship between the distance to main resources and the
262 observed number of hinds. The number of hinds within 50 metres of the main resource was
263 substantially higher in the estates where this resource was food supplementation than in the
264 remaining estates.

265 **DISCUSSION**

266 We found that food supplementation occurred on 19 out of 30 studied estates.
267 Moreover, when it occurred, food supplementation almost always determined hind
268 distribution, and was frequently the most important resource. Hind aggregation in estates
269 where food supplementation sites determined hind distribution was significantly higher than
270 in those where hind distribution was determined by other factors. As a consequence, mean
271 harem size was higher in those populations where hind distribution depended on food
272 supplementation. Therefore, food supplementation in red deer populations in south-western
273 Spain has become a management activity with a relatively high impact on mating system
274 features.

275 In spite of the high importance of food supplementation sites, natural factors also acted
276 as resources associated with hind distribution, although with lower frequency and importance
277 (Fig. 2). Green meadows were the natural factor with highest relative importance in hind
278 distribution. Green meadows are poorly represented in Mediterranean ecosystems during the
279 rutting season, because of the dry climatic conditions (Olea et al. 2005, Bugalho and Milne
280 2003). However, when green meadows are present, they always affect the red deer mating
281 system (Carranza et al. 1990, 1996) and in our results they appeared, when present, as the
282 most important environmental factor influencing hind distribution.

283 Collection of data on the distribution of animal individuals based on punctual
284 observations can bear an important random component. However, the variation in the results
285 of different measurements within the same population was low and presented very similar
286 predictive models for hind distribution (see online supplementary material).

287 The measure we used for hind aggregation depends on the density of females in the
288 population. Food supplementation could increase hind aggregation by increasing female
289 density through, for instance, increased survival or local immigration (Putman and Staines
290 2004). We found a trend towards higher hind density in estates in which hind distribution was
291 associated with food supplementation, although the effect was not consistent among estates
292 and regions and did not reach significance. In contrast, hind aggregation was consistently and
293 significantly higher in estates where hind distribution was associated with food
294 supplementation. Therefore, the main effect of food supplementation in our populations was
295 the local hind aggregation at estates offering food supplementation. Figure 4 shows that
296 beyond 50 meters from feeding sites the number of hinds tended to 0.

297 Hind distribution was significantly aggregated in all analyzed estates, independently of
298 the resulting model. Female aggregation is naturally related to a polygynous mating system
299 (Emlen and Oring 1977). As a consequence of female aggregation, males can monopolize

300 several females in harems (Shuster and Wade 2003). However, food supplementation
301 generates hind aggregation and harem size levels that are not reached by natural factors. In
302 polygynous mating systems, the spatial aggregation of females and the distribution of males'
303 breeding success are key elements in the operation of sexual selection (Andersson 1994).
304 Food supplementation is a new circumstance in Iberian red deer biology (around 6-10
305 generations) that may affect the opportunity for selection and evolution in populations
306 subjected to game management.

307 New circumstances can generate rapid evolution of populations in which genetically-
308 based phenotypic change takes place at a high rate (Thompson 1998, Hairston et al. 2005).
309 Such evolutionary changes have been observed within few generations (Singer et al. 1993),
310 within a single generation (Grant and Grant 1995) or even within a single season (Via and
311 Shaw 1996). The new situations created by the supplementary feeding might produce
312 behaviour-related phenotypic changes in Iberian red deer populations. High hind aggregation
313 levels induce male aggregation and an increase of individual interactions such as fights
314 among males and sexual harassment of males to females (Sánchez-Prieto et al. 2004). This
315 intensity of interactions increases the energetic demand of individuals which, as a
316 consequence, may change their behaviour (Geist 1982). This situation could change the
317 mating system from harem or territory defence polygyny (Clutton-Brock et al. 1982, Carranza
318 et al. 1990, 1995, 1996) to more polygynous systems such as the lekking system. Lek mating
319 is common in a related species, the fallow deer (*Dama dama*), where females tend to be more
320 aggregated and occur at higher local densities than red deer (Langbein and Thirgood 1989).
321 Lekking in fallow deer populations has been interpreted as a consequence of the sexual
322 harassment suffered by spatially clumped females (Clutton-Brock et al. 1993). Although true
323 leks have not been observed in red deer (Carranza 1992, 2000, Carranza and Valencia 1999),
324 a lek-like situation was already described for this species in Spain, where rutting males were

325 placed at fixed sites on the routes of female movement to supplementary feeding areas
326 (Carranza 1992). Heritable traits involved in male mating behaviour might experience new
327 selective pressures caused by food supplementation during the rutting season. High levels of
328 hind aggregation tend to increase the degree of polygyny (Emlen and Oring 1977, Shuster and
329 Wade 2003, Sánchez-Prieto et al. 2004), which, in turn, may raise the intensity of sexual
330 selection (Shuster and Wade 2003), with potential consequences on behaviour and structures
331 implicated in male-male competition (Andersson 1994, Kruuk et al. 2002).

332 Another potential consequence is related to changes in genetic diversity and non-
333 additive genetic components. Hind aggregation and mean harem size may increase the
334 variance in male mating success (Shuster and Wade 2003). This might reduce effective
335 population size, with possible consequences on the maintenance of genetic diversity
336 throughout generations (Nunney 1993, Briton et al. 1994, Falconer and Mackay 1996,
337 Frankham et al. 2002). However, hind aggregation could also favour the operation of
338 processes that tend to maintain genetic diversity. For red deer in Spain, Pérez-González et al.
339 (2009) showed that the level of polygyny was positively associated with a higher transmission
340 of genetic variability by the paternal lineage compared with the maternal lineage, which was
341 likely related to the advantage of heterozygous males in the competition for mates (Meagher
342 et al. 2000, Slate et al. 2000). Additionally, aggregation of individuals at certain areas may
343 favour female mate choice for dissimilar males, which has been shown to occur in Iberian red
344 deer (Carranza et al. 2009). We are just starting to understand some of these processes in red
345 deer populations and we are yet unable to say how supplementary feeding might affect them.

346 Supplementary feeding of Iberian red deer during the rut is a recent management
347 activity, and may be increasing due to the worsening climatic conditions in these areas.
348 Studies on climate change predict an increase of drought periods in Mediterranean areas
349 (Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change 2007). Scarcity of precipitation will decrease

350 resource availability for deer populations during the rut (Olea et al. 2005, Bugalho and Milne
351 2003) and managers may tend to increase the frequency and intensity of food supplementation
352 (Torres-Porras et al. 2009). The study of new selective pressures caused by food
353 supplementation is an important issue with potential evolutionary consequences for Iberian
354 red deer populations.

355 **Management implications**

356 Food supplementation during the summer and early autumn is a common practice in
357 Mediterranean ecosystems, and may be unavoidable in some circumstances to maintain deer
358 densities, economic yield, and reduce the impact of deer on shrub vegetation. However, it
359 becomes increasingly necessary to consider the potential evolutionary effects of management
360 practices in wild populations (Sutherland 2000). Supplementary feeding should be avoided
361 when possible. When necessary, its effects should be minimized by spatially dispersing the
362 supplementary food throughout the area of the estate to prevent excessive hind aggregation.

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517 **Figure captions**

518

519 Fig. 1. Study area and location of the 30 studied estates within Spain. A: estates in

520 Extremadura region; B: estates in Andalucía region.

521

522 Fig. 2. Importance of each resource on hind distribution. Plot shows the number of estates in

523 which each environmental factor is present (Present), the number of estates in which each

524 factor acted as a resource for hinds (Resource), the number of estates in which each factor

525 acted as the most important resource (Most important) and the number of estates in which

526 each factor acted as the second most important resource (2nd most important).

527

528 Fig. 3. Hind aggregation and mean harem size in different situations. Without Food Supp:

529 populations in which hind distribution was not determined by food supplementation sites.

530 With Food Supp: populations in which hind distribution was determined by food

531 supplementation sites. Plot shows means and standard errors (see Table 1).

532

533 Fig. 4. Effects of the distance to main resources on hind distribution. Figure shows the mean

534 and 95 % confidence intervals of the observed number of hinds within each 50-meter interval.

535 Without Food Supp: populations in which hind distribution was not determined by food

536 supplementation sites. With Food Supp: populations in which hind distribution was

537 determined by food supplementation sites.

538

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541

542 Table 1. Effects of environmental factors over hind distribution in each population (Pop).
 543 Table shows the number of counted hinds and the estimate slope (from the GLM) of the
 544 environmental factors that acted as resource in each population (see Fig 2 and online
 545 supplementary material).
 546

Pop	Hinds	Food supp	Crops	Green mead	Past cover	Past legum	Ponds	Streams
AC	128	-6.43				0.54	-38.27	
AL	128	-3.94				7.28		
AM	323	-19.36	-0.90					
AZ	66					4.87	-3.78	
BA	85	-4.88				1.46		
BB	30						-6.39	-9.18
CA	131	-16.34					-0.75	
CH	21	-22.23				2.27		
CL	74					1.59	-1.95	-5.30
CN	86					1.60	-2.69	-3.48
CV	231	-2.74			0.08			
ER	260	-44.04			0.37		-3.97	
ES	150	-2.42				0.46		
FV	193	-1.19						0.77
JA	64	-15.46					-9.40	-4.81
LS	142	-5.94	-46.95					
MEL	17							-4.97
MER	70			-18.19	3.26			
MM	108	-7.07						-0.60
MO	128	-11.28						-0.91
MS	27							-6.94
NA	17				3.84			
PA	34							-1.29
RM	85	-3.15				1.91	-0.81	-1.71
RO	96	-2.50			0.87	1.42		
SC	83		-16.61		1.84			-2.09
TA	79				1.60		-5.23	
US	225	-4.17						-0.22
VA	178	-2.55		-5.46		0.32		

547 Table 2. Comparison between populations in which hind distribution was and was not
 548 determined by food supplementation sites. Table shows the type of comparison (Dependent),
 549 the analysis used (Analysis), as well as the result of the models. Region: Extremadura or
 550 Andalucía; Food supp: Without Food Supp estates or With Food Supp estates; Sex ratio :
 551 number of males /number of females.

552

Dependent /Analysis	Effect	d. f.	F	P
Area/ANOVA	Intercept	1	23.156	< 0.001
	Region	1	2.353	0.138
	Food supp	1	0.009	0.925
	Region*Food supp	1	0.496	0.488
	Error	25		
Density/ANOVA	Intercept	1	10.253	0.004
	Region	1	1.905	0.180
	Food supp	1	3.587	0.070
	Region*Food supp	1	1.489	0.234
	Error	25		
Hind aggregation/ ANOVA	Intercept	1	14.029	0.001
	Region	1	0.053	0.820
	Food supp	1	8.660	0.007
	Region*Food supp	1	0.054	0.818
	Error	25		
Mean harem size/ General Linear Model	Intercept	1	109.922	< 0.001
	Sex ratio (covariate)	1	13.048	0.001
	Region	1	1.509	0.231
	Food supp	1	5.525	0.027
	Region*Food supp	1	0.292	0.594
	Error	24		
Sex ratio/ ANOVA	Intercept	1	89.017	< 0.001
	Region	1	2.960	0.098
	Food supp	1	1.989	0.171
	Region*Food supp	1	0.008	0.928
	Error	25		

553

554